

Timed automata to real-time simulate the ancillary service provision by a District Heating Multi-Energy System

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Abstract— This paper presents a simulation framework for the provision of auxiliary services by a multi-energy district heating system (MES) using timed automata (TA). Multi-energy systems are increasingly recognized as valuable assets due to their capability to operate across multiple energy vectors, thereby enabling the extraction of flexibility from diverse sources and delivering it to the electricity grid. The simulations developed in this study focus on the coordinated provision of multiple, concurrent auxiliary services by a pool of MES devices, which imposes stringent real-time coordination requirements. In this context, timed automata offer an effective modelling approach for capturing the temporal dynamics of such systems. The behaviour of the individual devices is governed by coordination strategies designed to fulfil the overarching objectives of the MES. These objectives include meeting energy demand, maintaining the balance among energy vectors, and ensuring the provision of auxiliary services upon activation by the system operator. Each coordination strategy is implemented through mixed-integer quadratic programming (MIQP) formulations.

Keywords— Multi-Energy Systems, Timed Automata, Flexibility, Ancillary Services, Optimization, Sector Coupling

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing need for power regulation on electrical grids is accelerating the search for new resources, particularly within distributed generation [1]. Supporting system regulation now requires integrating diverse resources, including those coupled with gas and heat systems—a priority reflected in the rising importance of multi-energy systems (MESs), [2] [3]. MESs operate across multiple energy carriers and spatial scales—local, to national—enabling service provision at various grid levels [4]. In the context of ancillary services (ASs), MESs enhance grid stability and power balancing [5], contributing through active power control, including primary, secondary, and tertiary reserves, power balancing, and congestion management. In Europe, balancing products are being restructured with platforms like TERRE (replacement reserve), MARI (manual restoration reserves), and PICASSO (secondary frequency restoration) currently being implemented, [2] [6].

For MESs, providing ASs offers economic opportunities, making technical and economic assessment essential. MES flexibility spans different carriers but must not jeopardize local energy supply. Flexibility in electricity can cause imbalances in coupled carriers like heat or gas, which must be managed. Addressing these cross-vector imbalances is a key cost MESs face when supporting system operators.

Developing a unified framework that captures the techno-economic constraints from devices, demand, and multi-market participation—typically non-linear and non-convex—is a challenging task. To address this, the proposed approach divides the modelling into two frameworks. The first operates at a coarse time resolution (e.g., hourly or 15-minute intervals), modelling high-level MES behaviour in response to demand and market commitments (proposed in [7]). The second one refines the output of the first step at a finer time resolution (e.g., seconds), incorporating detailed device and network dynamics. This step uses timed automata (TA) to handle non-linearities and forms the core of the work proposed in the early paper [8] and in the present one.

TA uses clock variables to model real-time operations [9] and supports both discrete and continuous processes, enabling hybrid computation [10]. They naturally represent concurrent control logic and offer flexible modelling of both linear and nonlinear physical processes. While advanced tools like Dymola/OpenModelica [11], MATLAB[®] and Python-based APMonitor [12], PyTorch [13], and PowerFactory [14] can accurately simulate heating, gas, and electricity systems, their complexity and modelling effort often limit adoption for small plants, where highly modelling costs are not justified.

The second-stage model employs control strategies to adapt automata behaviour to demand and operational constraints. The first strategy adjusts generation to meet demand and market commitments while keeping setpoints close to scheduled values. The second supervises the activation of ancillary services, coordinating devices involved in service provision and those maintaining energy carrier balance. This paper improves the framework presented in [8] ensuring the ancillary service provision does not affect the (heat) demand satisfaction and the importing/exporting exchanges of gas and electricity to fulfil the accepted energy market bids. The framework is also improved by a more accurate model of energy storing devices.

The paper is organized as follows, chapter II reports the modelling of MES behaviour, chapter III provides the details about the simulations of a real district heating MES, in standard operation and providing ancillary services, and conclusions recap the work and give an overview about next steps.

II. THE MODELLING OF MES BEHAVIOUR

A. Timed Automata

As proposed in [8], timed automaton (TA) [15] is a finite-state machine extended with real-valued variables, including clocks \mathcal{C} , and other physical quantities necessary to represent the behaviour of a real system. Clocks are used to model time constraints—typically the elapsed time since the last reset—allowing the automaton to account for temporal dependencies. The TA also interacts with its external environment through input and output data streams: input streams convey control commands, while output streams represent computed values of the system's physical variables. TA operates in a cyclic manner, with a fixed evaluation period denoted by Δ . Transitions between states are governed by logical conditions, which may also include time constraints. These transitions regulate the state evolution of the automaton and are assumed to have a minimum duration equal to the TA cycle, Δ . Formally, a TA can be defined by this tuple,

$$TA = \langle \Sigma_I, S, \Sigma_O, \mathcal{C}, \rightarrow \rangle \quad (1)$$

where Σ_I the set of *inputs*, S the set of *states* including the initial/final state s_0 . S is partitioned into *stationary* states, states for which all the transitions to the next states don't depend on time constraints; and *dynamic* states, states in which transitions are expressed by causal and timed constraints. Σ_O is the set of *outputs*, \mathcal{C} the set of *clocks*, ' \rightarrow ' the set of *transitions*. The set of inputs Σ_I includes the set of system-commands (e.g., *on-off* and *set-point*), the set of physical variables (e.g., the water flow rate, the input and output temperatures, etc.), the set of parameters (e.g., the duration of transition from two stationary states, expressed by clock constraints) and the set of rules required to calculate the dynamical behaviour according to the value of the set of physical inputs. Figure 1 shows a representation of the automaton interface. The system commands and the physical variables inputs are provided at each evaluation cycle, while the parameters and the rule are given for the whole simulation.

Figure 1 - The interface of an automaton

The set of output Σ_O includes the physical variables calculated by the automaton at each evaluation cycle. A transition ' \rightarrow ' links an initial state s_i to a final state s_j and fires when the associated *condition*- Γ , at state s_i with specific inputs, is verified,

$$\rightarrow : s_i \xrightarrow{\Gamma} s_j \quad (2)$$

A condition Γ has two main components: the *guard* (γ) and the *action* (α). Formally,

$$\Gamma \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \gamma : \alpha \quad (3a)$$

$$\gamma \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle \{(a \otimes b)^*\}, (c \oplus k) \rangle \quad (3b)$$

$$\alpha \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle \{(c = f(\underline{x}, c))\}, f_{out}(\underline{x}, c, p) = (\underline{y}) \rangle \quad (3c)$$

The intuitive semantics is 'a transition can fire when the *guard*- γ is *verified*', transition firing enables the execution of the *action*- α . In turn, the *guard*- γ is composed of a set of *logical* and *timed* conditions expressed by regular expressions (see eq (3b)), where $a \in \Sigma_I$, $\otimes \in \{=, \neq, >, \geq, \leq, <\}$, and the parameter b is a scalar ($b \in \mathbb{R}$). In the timed condition, $c \in \mathcal{C}$, $\oplus \in \{>, \geq, \leq, <\}$ and the parameter k is a scalar, $k \in \mathbb{R}$. In no-timed transitions, the guard time condition is empty.

Even the *action*- α has two components, the *action on the clock variables*, $c = f(c)$, and the *action on the output variables* $f_{out}(\underline{x}, c) = (\underline{y})$ (see eq (3c)). An action modifies the value of the clock variable $c \in \mathcal{C}$, increasing or resetting the clock by the function f . f_{out} defined in actions calculates the output variables $\underline{y} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_j\} \subseteq \Sigma_O$ according to input variables $\underline{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i\} \subseteq \Sigma_I$, the clock c , the set of parameters (p) and the set of rules possibly provided.

The simulation of a system consists in providing commands as input stream to the associated automaton, along a specified time horizon. The simulation result is reported on the output stream. The modelling of a system is validated according to the *behaviour equivalent assumption*. This consists, giving a stream of commands, in verifying whether the variable stream measured on the real device and the output stream calculated by the TA, (i.e., values of physical variables) agreed, cycle-by-cycle.

B. Pool of Automata and control strategies

In general, in a MES there are several (interacting) systems (i.e., devices), each of them modelled by a TA. Modelling the interactions among automata is a critical research topic, as witness in [16]. In this work it is assumed the simpler scheme, that is among automata there is no communication, then there is no automata evaluation priority (neither statically nor dynamically set).

The fulfilment of the MES objective is pursued by suitable coordinating strategies. Coordinating strategies apply to the outputs generated by device-automata in the previous cycle, the device set-points externally set and possibly other variables/parameters. Then they calculate the new set-point of the device-automata for the current cycle. In general, the evaluation of coordinating strategies is prioritized.

C. The modelling of MES behaviour

To address the topic of automata control, some preliminary definitions related to the characteristics of multi-energy systems are firstly introduced. A MES operates over a set of energy carriers denoted by $\mathcal{E} = \{\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2, \dots, \mathcal{E}_m\}$ (e.g., $\mathcal{E} = \{\text{power, heat, gas}\}$) and the set of devices \mathcal{D} are categorized into \mathcal{G} , \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{B} , where \mathcal{G} denotes generators, \mathcal{L} denotes loads and \mathcal{B} denotes storages. This categorization is energy carrier dependent, for instance a combined heat and power (*chp*) device acts as a generator on electricity and heat, but as a load on gas.

1) MES system automata

Each MES-system is modelled by a standardized timed automaton. The automaton's set of states includes: *stop* (s_0), *starting* (s_1), *run* (s_2), *changing set-point* (s_3), and *stopping* (s_4). States s_0 and s_2 are stationary (that is, the system can remain in these states indefinitely without time-based conditions) while s_1, s_3, s_4 are non-stationary states, that is the

system remains there at most for δ time instants (cycles). The value of δ is calculated when needed according to the characteristics of the device and the delta power required. The set Σ_I of input-commands includes the *unit-commitment* (uc), to control the on/off status of the device, and the *set-point* (sp), represented by a vector with one component per energy carrier, valued just for device enabled carrier. In case the device- d is a *chp*, the sp at time t is $\{\{p_d\}_{el}, \{p_d\}_{heat}, \{p_d\}_{gas}\}_t$ and hold the eqs (4a-4c).

$$\{p_d\}_{el} = \{p_d\}_{gas} \eta_d^{el,gas} \quad (4a)$$

$$\{p_{d,t}\}_{heat} = \{p_{d,t}\}_{gas} \eta_{chp}^{heat,gas} \quad (4b)$$

$$\{p_{d,t}\}_{\epsilon_i} = \{p_{d,t}\}_{\epsilon_j} \cdot \eta_d^{\epsilon_j, \epsilon_i} \quad (4c)$$

The set Σ_O of outputs includes all relevant physical variables that must be calculated by the automaton at each cycle. In the case of a *chp*, Σ_O typically includes at least the electrical, gas and heat powers. More generally, Σ_O may encompass a broader range of variables. For instance, those allowing to define the dependency of the heat produced with the device feeding and out temperatures, T_{in} and T_{out} , the mass flow rate Q and the water specific heat C_{pH2O} , and set in eq (5).

$$\{p_{d,t}\}_{heat} = (T_{in} - T_{out}) C_{pH2O} Q \quad (5)$$

This model can be captured by considering the physical variables T_{in} and Q as automaton-variables, and C_{pH2O} and T_{out} as input automaton-parameters.

Figure 2 - The timed automaton implementing a (no-storage) MES system. Dashed lines indicate non-stationary states.

The representation of a highly standardized device TA without storing ability, including its state set and transitions, is shown in Figure 2. Each transition, denoted as $T_{i,f}$, is depicted by an arc linking the initial (i) and final (f) states, and has associated *guards* and *actions*. Table 1 defines guards and actions for all transitions. Guards specify the conditions under which the firing of the transition is enabled and prescribe the action to be executed. Typically, the guard expresses conditions on uc , setpoint and clock variable c . The setpoint set in the previous cycle (sp) is distinguished from the current cycle input ($insp$). Actions determine the output values ($outs$) and update the clock variable c after transition fire. In the case of timed transitions, actions also define the time duration (δ_{ST} -starting, δ_{CSP} -changing sp and δ_{SP} -stopping) and the time dependent trend (\mathcal{J}) of the output values, according to the characteristics of the device.

Table 1 - Transitions of device automaton without storing

	guard				action			
	uc	sp	insp	c	c	δ	trnd	outs
T ₀₋₀	0	-	-	-				$\underline{0}$
T ₀₋₁	1	-	v	-	0	δ_{ST}	\mathcal{J}_{ST}	
T ₁₋₁	1	v	v	$<\delta_{ST}$	+1			$\mathcal{J}_{ST}(t)$
T ₁₋₂	1	v	v	$=\delta_{ST}$	0	0	[]	v
T ₂₋₂	1	v	v	-				v
T ₂₋₃	1	v	v ₂	-	0	δ_{CSP}	\mathcal{J}_{CSP}	
T ₃₋₃	1	v ₂	v ₂	$<\delta_{CSP}$	+1			$\mathcal{J}_{CSP}(t)$
T ₃₋₂	1	v ₂	v ₂	$=\delta_{CSP}$	0	0	[]	v ₂
T ₂₋₄	0	-	-	-	0	δ_{SP}	\mathcal{J}_{SP}	
T ₄₋₄	0	-	-	$<\delta_{SP}$	+1			$\mathcal{J}_{SP}(t)$
T ₄₋₀	0	-	-	$=\delta_{SP}$	0	0	[]	$\underline{0}$

Figure 3 - The Storage device model

In Figure 3 is provided the representation of the device TA with energy storing ability. The details of this automaton are not provided, however, the two meta-states ‘Discharging-phase’ and ‘Charging-phase’ represent each one the starting, running, changing setpoint and stopping of the discharging and charging phases, respectively. Furthermore, in each state in Figure 3 the calculation of the State of Energy (SoE) is performed at each cycle, that can lead the storage to the state *empty* or to the state *full* (of energy). In the empty state the only transition allowed leads to charging phase, in the latter the only transition leads to discharging.

D. The framework control strategies

As previously outlined, the TA-based simulation framework for real-time MES behaviour incorporates tailored control strategies designed to achieve system goal. This section defines two key control mechanisms: the load following with energy market bid alignment and the activation of ancillary services.

1) The control procedure to deal with ‘load following’ and energy market bid fitting

The goal of *load following* and *market fitting* is to minimize the absolute difference between, respectively, the system demand and the power generated/consumed by the MES, and the power exchanged with the grid and the quantities committed through accepted export/import bids. In Eq (6a), $p_{D,t}$ is the current demand and κ_{Lf} sets the threshold for activating the load-following strategy. In Eq (6b), the set \mathcal{D} of devices, M for day-ahead or intraday markets, ‘*’ stands for importing (+) or exporting (-) bid.

$$\left\{ \left(\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} p_{g,t}^{sp} \right) - p_{\mathcal{D},t} \right\}_{\varepsilon_i} > \kappa_{Lf} \quad (6a)$$

$$\left\{ \left(\sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} p_{d,t}^{sp} - p_t^{M,*} \right) \right\}_{\varepsilon_i} > \kappa_M \quad (6b)$$

These conditions are checked at each simulation step, with κ_{Lf} and κ_M tuned to simulation characteristics.

The market-fitting strategy ensures actual import/export trends match the accepted bids to avoid penalties. While load following and market fitting generally operate independently, their objectives may conflict. In such cases, the strategy may yield sub-optimal results, either partially meeting heat demand or incurring penalties. Algorithm 1 is activated when (6a) or (6b) are not satisfied.

Algorithm-1 computes set-point deviations for MES control devices over the upcoming interval starting at time t . It analyses a past horizon T_{past} to identify the deviation trends and predicts the counter measures over a future horizon T_{next} tailored to both the current deviation trend and device dynamics.

Algorithm-1 – Load following and market fitting strategies

$$\min_p \left\{ \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} (p_{d,t}^+ - p_{d,t}^{sp})^2 + (p_{d,t}^- - p_{d,t}^{sp})^2 \right\}_{\varepsilon_i} \quad \forall \varepsilon_i \in \mathcal{E} \quad (7a)$$

Such that

$$\left\{ \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} p_{d,t}^+ + \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} p_{d,t}^- = p_{\mathcal{D},t} \right\}_{heat} \quad (7b)$$

$$\left\{ \left(\sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} p_{d,t}^{sp} \geq p_{\mathcal{D},t}; p_d^- \leq p_d^{sp} \leq p_d^+ \text{ if } p_{d,t}^+ = 0 \right) \right\}_{heat} \quad (7c)$$

$$\left\{ \left(\sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} p_{g,t}^{sp} \leq p_{\mathcal{D},t}; p_d^{sp} \leq p_d^+ \leq p_d^- \text{ if } p_{d,t}^- = 0 \right) \right\}_{heat} \quad (7d)$$

$$\left\{ \left(\Delta_r = |p_r^{exc} - p_r^M| \ \& \ \Delta_r > \theta_r \ \& \ \left(I_r - E_r > 0 \ \& \ \Delta_r = \sum_{d \in \mathcal{G}} p_{d,t}^- + \mathbb{S}^- \right) \vee \left(I_r - E_r < 0 \ \& \ \Delta_r = \sum_{d \in \mathcal{G}} p_{d,t}^+ + \mathbb{S}^+ \right) \right) \right\}_{pow, gas} \quad (7e)$$

The Objective Function eq(7a) of ‘Algorithm-1’ is characteristics of a Mixed-Integer Quadratic Programming - MIQP scheme and forces the deviations, $p_{g,t}^+$ -upward, and $p_{g,t}^-$ -downward, to be as closed as possible to the current value $p_{d,t}^{sp}$. Deviations are set to recover the mismatches measured between the power generated by \mathcal{D} and the demand $p_{\mathcal{D},t}$, as well as those observed in fitting the accepted bids on electricity and gas energy markets. In eqs (7b-7d) the upward and downward deviations are set. Eq (7b), sets the mismatch between generation from devices \mathcal{D} and the demand. Eqs (7c) and (7d), bound the deviations. Eq (7e) ensures that the upward and downward deviations set provide the convergence towards the import and export accepted bids on the electricity and gas energy markets.

2) *Management of ancillary service activation*

The activation of ancillary services by the system operator (SO) follows country-specific regulations and market rules. The trading of these services is addressed during the MES operational planning stage (see [7]), where we assume a set of bids has already been accepted. As noted in [7], each bid may be fulfilled by multiple devices, while others support energy carrier balancing to meet market and demand commitments. Although multiple services can be activated simultaneously, this typically results from a sequence of SO

signals responding to specific grid events. Upon receiving an activation signal, the MES schedules the contributing devices based on the requested power, while triggering additional actions to maintain energy carrier balance. For instance, the SO activates the bid $p_{T_h}^{S_k}$, for the ancillary service \mathcal{S}_k , asking the amount of power $p_{\underline{t}}^{S_k(T_h)}$ ($p_{\underline{t}}^{S_k(T_h)} \leq p_{T_h}^{S_k}$) at time $\underline{t} \in T_h$, (T_h is the time instant where \mathcal{S}_k has been traded, with hourly time resolution, and \underline{t} is an element of T_h on seconds time scale). The operational dispatch of the set of devices $\mathcal{D}_{S_k(t)}$ involved in the activation is set by this equation.

$$p_{\underline{t}}^{S_k} = \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}_{S_k(\underline{t})}} p_{d,\underline{t}}^{S_k} \quad (8)$$

The activation of \mathcal{S}_k along the time interval $\{t_1, \dots, t_m\} \in T_h$ generally consists of a sequence of signals, $\{p_{t_1}^{S_k(T_h)} \dots p_{t_m}^{S_k(T_h)}\}$, (where $p_{t_i}^{S_k} \leq p_{T_h}^{S_k}$ for each t_i). Each activation is managed by MES as the power difference $\Delta_t^{S_k(\underline{t})}$ between the current $p_{t_j}^{S_k(T_h)}$ and the previous $p_{t_{j-1}}^{S_k(T_h)}$ (if any) activations. Next equation sets this difference,

$$\Delta_t^{S_k(T_h)} = p_{t_j}^{S_k(T_h)} - p_{t_{j-1}}^{S_k(T_h)} \quad (9)$$

Algorithm 2 optimizes the contributions from each device ensuring the provision of the activated power and the balancing of the energy carriers.

Algorithm - 2 – Management of service provision.

$$\min \left\{ \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}} \left(p_{d,t_j}^{S_k(T_h)} - p_{d,t_{j-1}}^{S_k(T_h)} \right)^2 \right\}_{\varepsilon_i} \quad (10a)$$

Such that

$$\left\{ \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}} p_{d,t_j}^{S_k(T_h)} = p_{t_j}^{S_k(T_h)} \right\}_{pow} \quad (10b)$$

$$\left\{ \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}} p_{d,t_j}^{S_k(T_h)} = \left(\sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}} p_{d,t_j}^{S_k(T_h)} \right) + p_{T_h}^{ID} \right\}_{\varepsilon_j} \quad \text{if } \varepsilon_j \neq pow \quad (10c)$$

$$0 \leq p_{d,t_j}^{S_k(T_h)} \leq p_d^{S_k(T_h)} \quad \forall d \in \mathcal{D}_{t_j}^{S_k(T_h)} \quad (10d)$$

$$0 \leq p_{d,t_j}^{S_k(T_h)} \leq \bar{p}_d \quad \forall d \in (\mathcal{D} - \mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}) = \mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}^- \quad (10e)$$

The objective function eq (10a), according to a MIQP scheme, minimizes the difference between the new and the former schedule for each device involved in the provision of the service $\mathcal{S}_k(T_h)$, and balancing energy carriers to stay as close as possible to the former value set $p_{d,t_{j-1}}^{S_k(T_h)}$. Eq (10b) schedules the contribution from the set of devices $\mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}$ at t , to supply the activated power $p_{t_j}^{S_k(T_h)}$, eq (10c) states the needed balancing actions on energy carrier(s) ε_j , different from pow , required by the service activation, in charge to the devices in $\mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}^-$, such that $\mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)} \cap \mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}^- = \emptyset$, and the bids on intra-day market (ID), $p_{T_h}^{ID} = p_{T_h}^{imp} - p_{T_h}^{exp}$. (10d) and (10e) set bounds for the contributions by the devices in $\mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}$ and in $\mathcal{D}_{S_k(T_h)}^-$, where \bar{p}_d is d power upper bound.

III. THE SIMULATIONS OF A REAL-MES

The simulation of an MES using timed automata (TA) models runs on a seconds-level timescale, enabling accurate verification of real-time constraints. Implemented in Python, the framework receives input commands from the daily plan

generated by the first-stage model. Each device automaton processes these inputs with its previous state to produce outputs. Control strategies may modify setpoints to better match demand or fulfil commitments like market bids. These adjustments respect device dynamics, which are simplified in the hourly model. For example, Figure 4’s hourly plan is refined in Figure 5 to a high-resolution version, highlighting the minimal demand fitting error achieved by control strategies. These strategies are implemented in Pyomo using the IPOPT solver [17].

A. The real-life example

The MES used in the simulations is a real district heating (DH) system in the Milan-East area, serving more than 700 buildings. The DH plant includes three co-generator gas engines (CHPs), each with a power range of 2.5–5 MW, a ramp rate of 0.25 MWe/min, and efficiencies of 0.43 (electrical) and 0.38 (thermal). Three gas boilers (GBs), rated at 0.3–14.5 MW with 0.87 efficiency, handle peak loads and fine heat-regulation. A geothermal heat pump (HP) supplies 12–13 MW of thermal power with a COP of 2.5. An electric boiler (EB), delivering 0.2–10.5 MW of heat at 0.99 efficiency, covers peak demand and fast ancillary services provider with 10 MW/min ramp. Two heat storage (HS) units, operated as one, offer 2–22 MW of charge/discharge and 58 MWh of energy, decoupling power, gas, and heat carriers.

The simulations of the Italian TSO ancillary services traded on the flexibility market consider the automatic (aFRR) and manual (mFRR) frequency restoration reserves products. aFRR has a full activation time (FAT) of 200 seconds and is symmetric. mFRR has upward and downward modes, each with a FAT of 15 minutes, and it is distinct in upward and downward products. All services are bided as 1-hour duration products. Of course, these parameters are configurable in the framework and can be adapted to the specific country regulation rules. The MES’s 24-hour schedule, set during short-term planning, is simulated at a seconds-level resolution. Figure 4 represents the hourly heat demand plan (the red dotted line) with device contributions (the coloured areas).

Figure 4 - A daily winter production schedule of MES with hourly time resolution

Figure 5 - The simulation of the daily MES program on seconds time resolution: heat demand is fit by the device generation

Figure 5 presents the second-scale simulation using timed automata: demand (red dotted line), total heat generation (blue line), and the resulting minimal fitting error (purple line), achieved via the load control strategy in Algorithm-1.

Figure 6 displays the scheduled daily AS program, derived from the flexibility resulted from meeting the heat demand. In this figure the contributions from several devices and the scheduling of several ancillary services traded at the same time instant are clearly highlighted. This ability (potentially) increases the MES remunerability.

Figure 6 – Results of the MES daily trading on TSO flexibility market

The three services considered are scheduled across various hours and power levels. aFRR (pink bars) is symmetric (as required by the current Italian rules), while mFRRdw (green) and mFRRup (blue) indicate negative and positive power, respectively. In Figure 6, dark colour bars represent the flexibility contribution from EB device, while light colour represent the flexibility contribution from CHPs. In Figure 7 are reported the details about the provision of the two services aFRR and mFRRup during hour 6 (see the yellow rectangle in Figure 6). The simulations of the sequence of activations, considering first the aFRR and then the mFRR upward (up) with the progressive deactivation of aFRR, is typical of SO event managing that faces the reduction of frequency nominal value. Figure 7(a) shows the power contribution for aFRR (yellow line) and the contribution for mFRRup (red line). aFRR activations are represented by pink vertical lines, while mFRRup activation are represented by blue vertical lines. The details about the simulation of the provision of aFRR and mFRRup are given in Figure 7(b1-b3).

Figure 7(b1) shows the activation of aFRR provided by EB (the red and yellow lines), and the EB program meeting the demand (the blue dotted line). EB reduces the electrical consumption, with respect to the standard program, and consequently “generates” electricity at the MES point of common coupling (pcc). The heat production is also reduced during this interval, the EB dynamics is so fast that power and heat lines overlap in the picture.

The contributions from CHP1 and CHP2 for the provision of mFRRup is shown in Figures 7(b2-b3), respectively. Service provision in this case consists in a first activation signal (the blue line) and the deactivation signal. The dynamics of CHP that is slower than the one of EB, and it is possible to appreciate the difference in increasing and decreasing trends of power (red line) and heat (yellow line).

The simulation outcomes of both the main daily program and ancillary service provision confirm that timed automata effectively model MES dynamics. Moreover, the MES

meets the strict requirements associated with providing ancillary services for grid frequency support. This framework enables the simulation of individual MES devices as well as their coordinated actions to achieve specific operational goals.

Figure 7 – Results of the simulation of the aFRR and mFRR provision by MES.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed a simulation framework for multi-energy systems (MESs) based on the timed automata (TA) modelling paradigm. Timed automata are well suited for capturing the dynamics of MES devices as they respond to demand and provide ancillary services while maintaining energy carrier balance. The ability of the framework was experimented with the simulation of TSO ancillary service provision operated by a real MES supporting district heating demand in the Milan area.

The TA modelling framework adopted requires explicit specification of time constraints, enhancing the precision and effectiveness of MES simulation. The hybrid extension of TA further enables the design of control strategies that more accurately tune device behaviour to meet MES objectives and account for the impact of physical variables. Future work will focus on analysing the interaction among multiple control strategies to reduce sub-optimal outcomes.

The next steps will widen the model of the set of ASs and devices in the MES, to increase the simulation abilities.

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